
Thermoplastic Infusion, In-Situ Polymerisation (TPIIP) and Double Diaphragm Forming (DDF) for Complex Parts at Scale

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FastBlade - World's First Regenerative Fatigue Test Facility

What We Do at FastBlade:

- Specialise in accelerated fatigue testing for tidal turbine blades
- Use advanced technology to simulate real-world conditions
- Develop novel tidal turbine blades and marine structures
- Aim to improve durability and performance of structures
- Collaborate on projects in renewable energy, aerospace, and other industries
- Work towards developing standards for the tidal sector

FastBlade - World's First Regenerative Fatigue Test Facility

Research projects:

- **MaxBlade** - Maximising tidal energy generation through blade scaling & advanced digital engineering

- **CoTide** - Developing and demonstrating holistic integrated tools and design processes for tidal stream energy

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Fibre Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites (TPC):

- Favoured for recyclability over landfill or pyrolysis
- Enables development of secondary markets

Importance:

- Growing demand across sectors like renewable energy, automotive, and aerospace.

Benefits:

- Welding
- Thermoforming
- Recyclability

Objectives and Significance

Objective: Address barriers to adopting reactive thermoplastic resin transfer moulding (RTM) for glass fibre reinforced polyamide 6 composites.

Significance:

- Enables research and smaller-scale production using polyamide-6 (nylon-6) thermoplastic systems through reduced equipment costs
- Industrial-scale machines of a similar type are prohibitively expensive
- Offers insights into high-quality composite manufacturing and improved mechanical properties

Industrial scale

Tabletop size

Methodology Overview

Materials Used:

- Monomer: ϵ -caprolactam
- Catalyst: Sodium caprolactamate
- Initiator: Hexamethylene-1,6-dicarbamoylcaprolactam
- Reinforcement: Polyester stitched UD glass fibre NCF

Equipment:

- Custom TP-RTM machine with heated tanks, gear pumps, and a static mixing head.
- Pneumatic press and aluminium mould for composite formation.

Process:

- Components heated and injected under low pressure.
- Polymerisation occurs in situ, forming the composite.

Manufacturing Process

Steps:

- Preparation: Drying of glass fibre fabric under vacuum.
- Injection: Low-viscosity monomers injected into the mould.
- Polymerisation: In-situ reaction forming polyamide 6 matrix.
- Cooling and Demoulding: Controlled cooling to ensure part quality.

Key Parameters:

- Injection pressure significantly lower than thermoset RTM.
- Temperature control critical for polymerisation and void reduction.

Polymerization and Manufacturing Process Overview

- After vacuum infusion, the reactant mixture polymerizes at 140–160 °C
- Benchmarked against Johns Manville's organosheet
- Successful infusion led to a manufacturing process using hot press tooling, demonstrating forming capabilities
- The "fill then form" process ensures even permeability before shaping, with polymerization below the 215 °C melt point allowing isothermal tool moulding

Figure 3: Results for in-plane shear testing comparing a flat panel produced using vacuum infusion between double diaphragms with two commercial organosheet panels (J. J. Murray *et al.*, *Materials & Design*, 2020).

Increasing TRL levels

- Constantly increasing TRL levels
- Equipment version progression
- Research collaborators
- Industry partners

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V1

V2

V3

V4

Benefits of DDF Process Variations

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- Process Variations:
 - Immediate Part Formation:
 - Uses two tough, stretchable polymeric films.
 - Forms liquid thermoplastic composite blank before final polymerisation.
 - Flat Pre-Polymer Blank Production:
 - Creates a semi-polymerised oligomer resin system.
 - Can be reheated, formed, and polymerised in a press, stabilized against moisture.

Three-part frame with central vacuum channel

Benefits of DDF Process Variations

Dr Andrew Parsons - UoN

- Advantages and Efficiency:
 - Reduces metal tooling needs, leading to significant capital savings despite a slight increase in bagging consumables.
- Fill-Form Process Sequence:
 - Lubricates fabric during forming.
 - Immediate forming follows infusion, reducing part wrinkling.

7) Final part de-moulded

DDF Process: Current work and Challenges

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- Process is temperature limited by available materials.
- Only Dahlar 9300Y, a high elongation fluoropolymer, meets mechanical and chemical demands.
- Bag strength is affected by temperature, risking pin-holing in high strain areas.
- Process is limited to a 145 °C ceiling for the tea tray tool.

Figure 1: Temperature dependence of bagging in equibiaxial testing results.

Figure 2: Pin-holing observed at regions of high strain.

Summary: custom TP-RTM machine and the developed process

- Enables research which would not otherwise be possible due to high entry and operational costs
- Allows development work in thermoplastic (PA6), composite and other hybrid systems
- Project benefits from multidisciplinary expertise from a range of industrial partners and research institutions
- Happy to collaborate and develop custom solutions

Tabletop size

Thank you!